

THE IMPACT OF SECOND LANGUAGE TO HUMAN BRAIN

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Abstract The article will discuss the impact of second language to human brain and its benefits. The authors explain not only how second language learning beneficial for human brain but also they suggest some recent research results which can be a good evidence of their ideas.

Keywords: brain, language, learning, skills, short- and long-term memory, bilingual, multilingual, multitask.

Introduction

We all know there are great benefits to learning a new language. Languages are gateways to new cultures, allowing us to connect with others from different places around the world in ways more meaningful than before. But learning a new language has physical health benefits as well. Let’s take a look at some of the latest research on the effects of learning a new language on the human brain.

Main part

Learning a language is a way to protect the brain against ageing because it promotes ‘neuroplasticity’ (the brain’s ability to develop new neural pathways). It helps you gain a new perspective on the world around you and trains your brain to handle a wide range of challenges. Classes and courses are great ways to do this. They engage cognitive skills, such as visual comprehension, short- and long-term memory, attention to detail, and even math and calculations which goes a long way in improving your brain health. The brain contains areas that are specialized to deal with language, located in the perisylvian cortex of the left hemisphere. These areas are crucial for performing language tasks, but they are not the only areas that are

used; disparate parts of both right and left brain hemispheres are active during language production. In multilingual individuals, there is a great deal of similarity in the brain areas used for each of their languages. Insights into the neurology of multilingualism have been gained by the study of multilingual individuals with aphasia, or the loss of one or more languages as a result of brain damage. Bilingual aphasics can show several different patterns of recovery; they may recover one language but not another, they may recover both languages simultaneously, or they may involuntarily mix different languages during language production during the recovery period. These patterns are explained by the dynamic view of bilingual aphasia, which holds that the language system of representation and control is compromised as a result of brain damage [1] .

The ability to communicate with respect and cultural understanding in more than one language is an essential element of global competence. This competence is developed and demonstrated by investigating the world, recognizing and weighing perspectives, acquiring and applying disciplinary and interdisciplinary knowledge, communicating ideas, and taking action. Global competence is fundamental to the experience of learning languages whether in classrooms, through virtual connections, or via everyday experiences. Language learning contributes an important means to communicate and interact in order to participate in multilingual communities at home and around the world. This interaction develops the disposition to explore the perspectives behind the products and practices of a culture and to value such intercultural experiences [3].

Learning a new language is a wonderful benefit in a globalized world. Let's have a look at some of the benefits of learning a second language.

1. It improves your memory

The more you use your brain to learn new skills, the more your brain's functions work. Learning a new language pushes your brain to get familiar with new grammar

and vocabulary rules. It allows you to train your memory to remember new words, make connections between them, and use them in contextual situations.

2. Enhances your ability to multitask

Time management and multitasking are two skills that will always help you. Multilingual people have the ability to switch between languages. Their ability to think in different languages and be able to communicate in more than one language helps with multitasking.

3. Improves your performance in other academic areas

Fully immersing yourself in a language learning environment means not only learning the basics of that language. It means learning how to communicate in another language with your peers or participating in extracurricular activities in that specific language [4] .

Recent evidence has suggested that there is a positive impact of bilingualism on cognition - with a later onset of dementia. Researchers from the University of Edinburgh used the Lothian Birth Cohort 1936 to address wasn't learning a second language can influence later cognitive performance. Disco halt offered the opportunity to address confounding variables such as ethnic and environmental differences.

The researchers found that bilinguals performed significantly better on tests conducted between 2008 and 2010. The strongest effects were observed on general intelligence and reading. Overall results suggested a positive effect of bilingualism on cognition in older age and this included those who acquired a second language as adults. The bilingual executive advantage (BEA) hypothesis, that is, the improvement in cognitive functions, specifically executive functions, results from the ability to control more than one language system. This theory is controversial, and a recent systematic review, including 53 studies, does not apply to working memory. There is evidence to support the bilingual effect in relation to cognitive

flexibility. However, the inconsistent results found across studies prevent clear conclusions from being drawn; further studies are still needed [2] .

These benefits are essential for and are within reach of all learners. An early start to learning a second language and sustained learning sequences show strong results in helping all learners achieve these results. Those whose native or heritage/family language is not English also must be supported to develop skills to function and interact in their heritage language and culture, which also benefits their acquisition of English language proficiency. All learners benefit from programs that support them as autonomous learners and that provide engaging and motivating activities and assessments

Conclusion

The truth is, learning new skills every day enhances all aspects of person's life. By learning new skills, you can increase your career opportunities, find out more about the world around you, and be a better person overall.

List of used literature:

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